

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Gareyeva Galina Ramil kizi

THE PROVERB IS A SPECIFIC LINGUISTICAL AND COGNITIVE SPACE FOR THE REALIZATION OF THE SPIRITUAL
EXPERIENCE AND MORAL VALUES OF THE PEOPLE (IN MATERIALS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

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